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Sloshing Wing Dynamics - 2nd Year Project Overview

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The SLOshing Wing Dynamics (SLOWD) project aims to investigate the modelling of fuel sloshing physics to reduce the design loads on aircraft structures. This goal will be achieved through investigating the damping effect of sloshing on the dynamics of flexible wing-like structures carrying liquid (fuel) via the development of experimental set-ups complemented by novel numerical and analytical tools. The primary focus of the project is the application of modelling capabilities to the wing design of large civil passenger aircraft (subject to EASA CS-25 type certification), which are designed to withstand the loads occurring from atmospheric gusts, turbulence and landing impacts. The timeframe of the project is three years, starting in September 2019. This paper reviews the current progress that has been made and outlines goals for the rest of the project.

I. Introduction

LARGE passenger aircraft produced in the European Union are designed to meet the regulatory requirements of Certification Specification 25 (CS25), as defined by the airworthiness authority - the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA). The wings of such aircraft are highly flexible structures, which can deform significantly when, for example, atmospheric turbulence or a gust is encountered. Typical limit deformations can reach 20% of the wing span. Wings also house the fuel tanks, and generally carry an amount of fuel comparable in weight to that of their

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structural components. For a typical wing of a single aisle aircraft, with maximum take-off weight of 100 tonnes and 3000nmi range, both structural and fuel weights are of the order of 4 to 6 tonnes. The standard engineering practices for wing (and aircraft) design do not consider the effect of the fuel movement within the tanks for the determination of the aircraft design loads, owing to the lack of validation of the current toolsets available to industry. In fact the typical aircraft development cycle includes two major types of tests to identify/verify the dynamic characteristics of the aircraft structure and its characteristic excitations:

- Ground Vibration Test (GVT), performed before first flight. The aircraft is made to vibrate by mechanical means so that its structural behavior (including damping) can be measured. It is standard practice to repeat the test for the two extreme conditions of either empty or full tanks.
- Flutter Flight Test (FFT), usually performed via prescribed oscillatory motion of the aircraft control surfaces (such as ailerons) when flying at speed close to the design envelope of the aircraft. Results from the FFT campaign are used to adjust the unsteady external aerodynamic model and to validate the aeroelastic behaviour and stability bounds.

Both above tests are limited to small amplitudes and are therefore not likely to excite significant sloshing modes.

In the case of the GVT, this is to avoid damaging the specimen (usually the first production aircraft), and the FFT to avoid endangering the safety of crew and aircraft. Also significant is that these qualification tests are performed after the design of the fuel tanks is finalized.

The EASA certification specifications offer the possibility to relax the conservatism inherent to these industrial practices, in fact the CS-25 Acceptable Means of Compliance (AMC) 25.341 6. c. (Gust and Continuous Turbulence Design Criteria) state: *"Structural dynamic models may include damping properties in addition to representations of mass and stiffness distributions. In the absence of better information, it will normally be acceptable to assume 0.03 (i.e. 1.5% equivalent critical viscous damping) for all flexible modes. Structural damping may be increased over the 0.03 value to be consistent with the high structural response levels caused by extreme gust intensity, provided justification is given"*. Therefore, SLOWD aims at quantifying, via a holistic approach (both experimental and numerical), the extent to which liquid sloshing in the aircraft tanks affects the "structural damping" mentioned in the AMC above, or more in general the structural dynamic behavior of an airliner, at "high structural response levels". In addition, the identification of the architectural parameters to maximize fuel slosh induced damping will overcome the major shortfalls of the current industrial practices: conservatism in the design loads calculation and inability to maximize the benefits related to sloshing-induced dissipative effects (via informed design of the fuel tank layout). A substantive increase in the damping characteristics of the structure is expected, as recently demonstrated experimentally by the preliminary work performed by Airbus in collaboration with all the SLOWD consortium partners [1, 2]. Interestingly, similar experiments have been performed in the 1950's by NACA (Ref. [3]) with similar findings on the effective damping of the structure, but limited characterization of the liquid flow.

The paper is organised as follows; a brief overview the project and the partners involved is given in section II, sections III IV V describe the experimental and fundamental numerical work related to fluid and structural dynamics, sections VI VII detail the progress made in the modelling of fluid-structure interaction problem via high-fidelity and reduced order models, finally the outline of future work is provided in the conclusive section VIII.

II. Project Organization

The main goal of the project (Ref. [4]) is to define a holistic approach (both experimental and numerical) to quantify the energy-dissipation effects associated with the liquid movement inside aircraft fuel tanks, as the wing undergoes dynamic excitations. This goal is divided into four specific objectives:

- Setup of an Experimental Campaign to investigate the response to dynamic loading of the wings of a modern passenger airliner (200 passengers or more) carrying fuel. The results of the campaign will be a database of measurements for benchmarking the numerical and analytical methods developed during the remainder of the project. The measured quantities will include time-varying parameters (e.g. accelerations, displacements, wall pressures) from which the damping effect of the slosh will be computed.
- Further development of numerical methods for the concurrent modelling of the experimental setup. The aim of the modelling is twofold; preliminary calculations will be undertaken to inform the design of the experimental campaign. Subsequently, a high-fidelity digital-twin of the experimental set-up will be generated, which will provide a wealth of data from which reduced order models can be built. The numerical methods are to be

implemented in executable software and made available to all partners on a common computing environment for purposes of the project.

- Evaluate Reduced-Order and Analytical Models, as reduction in the complexity of the numerical models is deemed necessary for subsequent inclusion into an industrial design framework. Several reduced-order and analytical models will be evaluated in terms of their computation efficiency and accuracy in predicting sloshing-related dissipative effects. As per the numerical methods, the methods for deriving ROMs are to be implemented in executable software and made available to the partners on a common computing environment for the purposes of the project.
- Integration of the Models into a Multidisciplinary Design Framework. An industrialised version of the software developed in b) and c) will be used to understand the influence of design parameters such as baffle spacing, baffle openings, fill-level to define an optimal architecture of the wing fuel tanks, which maximises the dissipation effects due to fuel sloshing.

Fig. 1 Consortium Geographical Composition.

Participant organisation name	Country	ID
AIRBUS OPERATIONS LIMITED (Coordinator)	United Kingdom	AO
ARIANEGROUP GMBH	Germany	AG
AIRBUS DEFENCE AND SPACE GMBH	Germany	ADS
EASN TECHNOLOGY INNOVATION SERVICES BVBA	Belgium	EASN
UNIVERSITY OF CAPE TOWN	South Africa	UCT
UNIVERSITY OF BRISTOL	United Kingdom	UB
UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA LA SAPIENZA	Italy	USRS
UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	Spain	UPM
UNITED KINGDOM RESEARCH AND INNOVATION	United Kingdom	UKRI
CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	Italy	CNR

Table 1 Consortium Partners.

To achieve this objectives, the partners of the SLOWD project formed a consortium, bringing together industrial know-how and academic research. The institutions involved are listed in Table 1 and their geographical location is shown in Fig 1. The research activities of the partners have been organised according to the work break-down structure depicted

Fig. 2 Work Break-Down Structure.

in Fig. 2, where the leader institution for each Work Package (WP) is shown given in brackets. As shown graphically in Fig. 2, WP2-4 are considered as fundamental building blocks to understand experimentally and numerically the physical phenomena associated with the increased damping due to sloshing, while WP5 and WP6 aim at modeling the coupled Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) problem with high fidelity and reduced order models. In reminder of the paper we focus on the work carried out within WP2-6, and reserve more in depth description of WP7 and WP8 to future publications.

III. Experimental Work (WP2)

The consortium setup a series of experimental campaigns to investigate the response to dynamic loading of the wings of a modern passenger airliner carrying fuel. The results of these campaigns are a database of measurements for benchmarking the numerical and analytical methods developed under the other work-packages of the project. The measured quantities include time-varying parameters (e.g. accelerations, displacements) from which the damping effect of the sloshing can be computed, as well as flow imaging of the sloshing liquid in the tanks. The overall strategy behind the physical testing is depicted in the diagram in Fig. 3, which shows the relative cost and complexity of the different test types in relation to the number of parametric variations.

Fig. 3 Experimental Test Strategy.

The low-complexity *Prototype* test was setup prior to the start of the project at their Airbus Protospace laboratory in Filton (UK), and is described in Ref. [1, 2]). The rig comprised of a water tank mounted on a 2.35m cantilever and an accelerometer fixed at the free end of the beam. The cantilever was forced into a deflected shape by the ratchet and quick-release mechanism. Once the quick-release was activated, the cantilever was free to oscillate and the decay in the

oscillation was recorded by an accelerometer, as shown in Fig. 4. The configuration was broadly representative of a wing and its fuel tank undergoing a step-input type of excitation (similar to that due to a gust).

Fig. 4 Prototype Test Acceleration Measurement (top) and Visualization of Liquid Flow (bottom) during the Initial Oscillation.

The time traces shown in Fig. 4 compare two cases, with the tank carrying a weight equal to 7% of the mass of the cantilever for both. This is the typical design condition for a large aircraft wing. In the “liquid mass” case, the tank was filled with water to 50% of its maximum capacity, while in the “solid mass” case the tank carried the same mass of solid material (ballast). Note that for ease of comparison the vertical response for each case (solid ballast and liquid) is normalised with respect to their own initial peak acceleration. It can be seen from comparison of the acceleration decays over time that the liquid motion in the tank, induced by the free vibration of the beam, damps the oscillations faster than in the solid case. The time to decay to half of the maximum acceleration can be considered here as a first order indicator of the damping characteristic of the oscillating system. In the liquid case about four oscillations ($t = 0.452s$) are needed for the acceleration to decay to half its maximum amplitude, compared at least six oscillations ($t = 0.757s$) in the solid case, therefore indicating 50% increase in the damping characteristics of the system.

At the opposite end of the spectrum in terms of complexity, the *Real-Scale* wing test is planned for the final phase of the project. The test concept is similar to previous tests performed at Airbus (Ref. [5]) to measure structural damping at high oscillation amplitudes, away from the typical linear regime measured during the GVT. To ensure a high amplitude response, the wing specimen will be deflected close to its maximum structural capability using a quick-release mechanism and a loading collar. After a settling time for the liquid to find its equilibrium position, the wing will be suddenly released, leaving the structure and the liquid in its interior tank free to oscillate, similarly to the *Prototype* test. The additional complexity of the *Real-Scale* test is considered necessary for a reliable complex model validation. In fact the setup will provide a benchmark method to comply with aforementioned AMC 25.341 and ensure its applicability to aircraft certification programs. The actual specimen will comprise a realistic wing configuration with a span of the order of 16m, similar to the Airbus A320 family, with and without liquid to assess the effect of sloshing on its dynamic behavior. Due to the large scale, and consequent cost (the force required to achieve limit deflection for a wing of this size is of the order of 15 metric tons), the range of excitations and parameters investigated will be relatively limited, focusing on the expected biases between real and small scale.

To precede the *Real-Scale*, a similar testing campaign will take place at *Small-scale* with a wing specimen of the span of the order of 3m (scale 1:5), see Fig. 5. More details about the design and the scaling used in the design of the test specimen are given in Ref. [6]. In the context of the overall strategy, the small-scale test will be performed to:

- De-risk the real-scale test, as free release tests are highly dynamic events which require assessment of the structural integrity of the wing specimen and testing equipment sensors.

Fig. 5 Small Scale Wing Test Specimen.

- Provide an early benchmark set of results for the validation of the numerical methods developed in the remainder of the project. Note that compared to the *Prototype* test, the *Small-scale* test will introduce additional complexity (e.g. fully three-dimensional wing geometry, coupled bending/torsion excitations).
- Allow for the installation of a broad range of sensing and excitation equipment, for the monitoring of both liquid and solid phases. As an example, high speed cameras and specialized lighting will be employed to observe the liquid free surface, which are unlikely to be installed on the real-scale specimen due to limited access to the fuel tanks. Also, due to the reduced scale, it might be feasible to employ external excitation devices to apply external forces for the validation of active control strategies.
- Allow for a large range of parameters to be investigated, thanks to the reduced cost. As an example, the amount of testing liquid required for the *Real-Scale* test is estimated at 1.5 metric tons, in contrast to 10kg for the *Small-Scale* test. Therefore, different liquids of various densities and viscosities will be tested. Another practical aspect for consideration is testing with a solid mass equivalent to the liquid (for comparison with the current industrial practices). This is impractical at real-scale due to the high volumes required and the limited access to the fuel tanks, but will be part of the small-scale tests.

In the early phases of the project, it became apparent that no literature exists about flows as energetic as the ones under consideration within SLOWD. Consequently a number of experimental rigs, shown in Fig. 6, have been developed and fundamental data generated to explore the characteristics of vertical sloshing in different tanks subjected to transient and harmonic vertical excitation, at the University of Bristol (Ref. [7–10]), the Polytechnic University of Madrid (Ref. [11, 12]) and the University of Rome LaSapienza (Ref. [13, 14]). This series of tests are labelled single-degree-of-freedom, or *1 DOF* in Fig. 3.

The key findings have been that the response and effective damping depends upon the amplitude and frequency of the motion, the amount of fluid and fill level, but is less sensitive to the fluid properties (such as viscosity and surface tension). These considerations informed the design of the *Small-Scale* test, as described in Ref. [6].

IV. Fluid Dynamics (WP3)

In WP3, three in-house Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) codes were employed to simulate the behaviour of a liquid subject to violent vertical motion. The open literature contained no explicit quantification of violent slosh induced damping due structurally induced vertical excitation, therefore several of the experimental test cases carried out as part WP2 were selected to validate the numerical results. In particular, Fig. 8 and 10 show a comparison of the external work W_{ext} normalized by the potential energy $\Delta\mathcal{E} = mg\Delta h$, where m is the fluid mass, g is the gravitational acceleration and Δh is the maximum change in tank vertical position. In the experiments the tank was mounted on springs, as seen in Fig. 6(b), moved away from equilibrium and suddenly released. The dominant frequency of the resulting motion is $f = 6.51Hz$ and the related period $T = 1/f$ has been used to scale time in all plots. CFD was also used to complement the non-dimensional analysis studies performed in WP2, to simulate a range of parameters beyond what achievable with the reduced scale of the *1 DOF* tests, see Ref. [15–17].

Standard CFD schemes used today for the purpose of slosh loads predictions are based on the incompressible Volume of Fluid (VoF) method. This however results in the over-prediction of pressure spikes and slow simulations due matrix conditioning in the case of violent slosh. Consequently the Elemental[®] software, developed by the University of

Fig. 6 Experimental Test Rigs - (a) Univ. of Bristol, (b) Polytechnic Univ. Madrid, (c) Univ. Rome LaSapienza.

Cape Town (UCT), was extended to model slosh impact loads via both fully compressible (all Mach number) as well as weakly compressible formulations. With regards the all-Mach number fully compressible formulation, a novel scheme was developed which combines the Hartens-Lax-van Leer Contact (HLLC) solver with the Volume-of-Fluid (VoF) method. For SLOWD applications, the gas compressibility effects were demonstrated significant, but only to the extent requiring a weakly compressible formulation. Additional novel developments in Elemental[®] included the introduction of a momentum conservative HiRAC VoF scheme, accounting for turbulence via LES (Large Eddy Simulation) and accurate surface tension and contact angle modelling. All of these were required to account for the initial Rayleigh Taylor instabilities prevalent in the sloshing flow under consideration. Due to the state-of-the-art nature of this work, it resulted in several conference and journal publications, Ref. [16–19].

Fig. 7 VOF Simulations - Free Surface Configuration.

An alternative approach to the more standard mesh-based CFD methods is Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH), which represents the fluids as an ensemble of particles. The industrial code SPH-Flow was enhanced by the Institute of Marine Engineering of CNR to model the experimental test cases. Consistently for the two and three dimensional simulations, the weakly-compressible δ -LES-SPH method was adopted, accounting for turbulence via a Large Eddy Simulation model. Only the liquid phase was considered in the modelling, with considerable advantage in terms of computation time, and the role of surface tension was taken into account only in the initial conditions by introducing a liquid meniscus at the intersection between the wall and the free surface. This SPH model, developed by CNR, represents the current state-of-the-art of SPH schemes for turbulent flows, Ref. [20–26]. Figure 9, similarly to Fig. 7, show the first liquid roof impact, with the characteristic "fingers" due to the development of the Rayleigh-Taylor instability during the first oscillation cycle.

The Polytechnic Univ. Madrid (UPM) modelled the common test case, with similar results to UCT and CNR, using the open-source code AQUAGPUSPH, but also extended the analysis developing a multiphase delta-WCSPH

Fig. 8 VOF Results - Normalized Work Done on the Fluid.

Fig. 9 SPH Simulations - Free Surface Configuration.

Fig. 10 SPH Results - Normalized Work Done on the Fluid.

code. Surface tension was also taken into account while both periodic and no-slip wall boundary conditions were implemented. As first step, validation against a well-established benchmark case involving the Rayleigh Taylor instability was performed. As shown in Fig. 11, the developed code proved able to capture the linear regime present at the initial stages of the simulation. The multiphase SPH formulation was further found robust for a wide range of densities and viscosities. This work results in several publications, Ref. [15, 27, 28].

The CFD analysis performed allowed to better understand the underlying phenomena associated with the sloshing in wing tanks, and particularly the liquid to wall and liquid to liquid impact, with the associated turbulent energy cascade from the large to small vortices. Both the VoF and SPH methods achieved good accuracy in comparisons with the experimental results, even if full numerical converge was not achievable due to the large range of scales in the sloshing flow. In the next phase of the project both methods will be the building block for the coupled FSI simulation.

Fig. 11 SPH Simulation of Rayleigh Taylor Instability.

V. Structural Dynamics (WP4)

The structural dynamics work-package addressed the need to establish validated reference models suitable for further FSI studies, and was informed by the Airbus research activities related to the *Real-Scale* test. The models are to be validated using inputs from WP2, and should be representative of flexible “dry” structure in the linear and nonlinear regimes.

Fig. 12 Full Scale Wing Finite Element Model - First Natural Mode.

Airbus developed a Nastran Finite Element (FE) model of the *Real-Scale* test specimen described in WP2, see Fig. 12. The modelling activity required the adaptation of a static stress model to include lumped mass model adequate to represent the dynamic behaviour of the wing. This model was taken as reference by the University of Bristol for *Small-Scale* experiments, which required a 1:5 geometrical scaling. The design of the *Small-Scale* wing specimen utilized a ladder-like architecture, whilst maintaining some other key geometric features such as the wing planform, sweep and an optional dihedral angle of the *Real-Scale*. The liquid tank was positioned above the plane of the ladder (see Fig. 5), to allow for unimpeded flow visualization. The corresponding FE model was developed concurrently, with particular attention to the interface between the tank and the structure. A two-stage sizing process was used, which parameterized the three-dimensional beam structure to match the *Small-Scale* FE model with *Real-Scale* reference. In the first stage, the two structures were optimally matched for three static deflection patterns using a single-objective Genetic Algorithm optimizer and a set of the sectional stiffness parameters. In the optional second stage, point masses elements were used to improve the modal match. At the interface between the structure and the tank, a system of custom-built semi-rigid interface elements (modelled using the standard FE bush elements) was designed to ensure low interfacial damping, controlled load transfer, and minimized pre-stressing of the constituent substructures under moderate deflections. The University of Rome LaSapienza developed the capability to import a modal representation of the FE models into the Simulink environment, facilitating the coupling of the structural models with the Reduced Order Models (ROMs) of WP6.

These developments were key enablers for several activities including the preparation of a test definition document for the *Real-Scale* test, the manufacturing of the specimen for the *Small scale* test, the implementation and testing of structural component into the coupled FSI problem of WP5 and WP6 (Ref. [29]). Future work will extend the applicability of the models to the non-linear regime, to account for shortening effects and their influence on the dynamic of the sloshing fluid.

VI. High-Fidelity FSI (WP5)

WP5 aims at the concurrent modelling of the experimental setups of WP2, and involves the development of coupling methodology for the numerical models developed in WP3 and 4. The aim of the modelling is twofold; preliminary calculations will be undertaken to inform the design of the experimental campaign; subsequently a high-fidelity

digital-twin of the experimental setups will be generated, to provide data for the calibration of reduced order models (WP6). Owing to the large computational costs expected from the high-fidelity calculations, this modelling framework will be implemented in a massively-parallel high-performance computing environment (HPC) to enable its use in the industrial design process of civil aircraft. Figure 13 gives a graphical representation of the CFD/FEM coupling and shows the type of models and information exchanges involved in the numerical coupling.

Fig. 13 Fluid Structure Interaction with Active Control.

A key output of WP5 is a tested FSI software framework capable of solving the use-cases demanded by the SLOWD project. Currently internal processes within Airbus rely on Nastran for structural analyses, the primary framework developed by the SLOWD project is therefore based around this commercial solver. The goal of the project is also to produce a framework capable of employing different CFD methods to explore problems using the most appropriate workflow, and in particular the Volume of Fluid mesh-based solver Elemental[®] and the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics particle-based solver SPH-flow developed in WP3. Previous work undertaken by Airbus and the University of Bristol (Ref. [30]) has shown that it is possible to create a suitable FSI framework by employing the OpenFSI interface provided by MSC to enable Nastran for this kind of purpose. However further developments of coupling solution were deemed fundamental, to allowed for the use of HPC and to improve computational efficiency in the data transfer between solvers. Therefore the Multiscale Universal Interface (MUI) code coupling library was selected as the underlying connecting element (Ref. [31]). This library is open-source and free to use and developed by members of the consortium (UKRI-STFC), it is designed to facilitate HPC-oriented code couplings without significant knowledge of how to organise the complex communication patterns needed. As the framework relies on Nastran and the coupling capability provided by OpenFSI, the overall design was dictated by this component. It was impossible to incorporate a suitable method for transferring data between solvers in a partitioned solution for use in a distributed memory HPC environment, therefore an approach in which a proxy application called the AirBusInter (ABI) application has been created. This is executed separately to Nastran/OpenFSI but communicates directly with it via a shared memory data structure. The MUI coupling library was embedded into the ABI application and this handles inter-solver communication. An overview of the communication protocol between this different components is shown in Fig. 14. The design also included the TimeControl service object provided by MSC under contract to the SLOWD project and developed by Hexagon Software Ltd.

Finally, building on an existing design developed by UKRI-STFC, an alternative open-source framework has been developed in parallel with the commercial solution (Ref. [32]), this is also based on MUI but utilises freely available structural and fluid solvers. Fundamentally, it provides a similar coupled solution to the main commercial option, offering a validated and easily developed test framework for the consortium to collaborate around where not all have direct access to source code in the case of the commercial solvers. This framework mitigates risk within the project as it can be rapidly developed and presents a simulation alternative to the commercial solvers.

The software framework was completed and tested on the HPC system using exemplar explicit and implicit fluid solvers. Work to integrate and test the chosen commercial fluid solvers is currently ongoing. In the final phase of the SLOWD project the framework is expected to be use to model the *Real-Scale* wing test in its full complexity.

Fig. 14 Calculation Framework for the FSI Problem.

VII. Reduced Order Models (WP6)

In WP6 a variety of reduced-order and analytical models will be evaluated in terms of their computation efficiency and accuracy in predicting sloshing-related dissipative effects. The reduction in the complexity of the numerical models is necessary for subsequent inclusion into an industrial design framework. In fact the CS25 regulations require performing a large number of computations, for which experimental (WP2) or high-fidelity (WP5) models are prohibitively expensive. Advanced data analytics techniques were explored to build these Reduced Order Models (ROMs), utilizing the experimental and numerical data generated in the other work packages. As shown in 13, the ambition is then to be able to replace the high-fidelity models in the calculation framework with a reduced-order counterparts.

The University of Rome LaSapienza formulated the general theory for an input/output sloshing reduced order model based on the Linearized Frequency Domain (LFD) identification approach. These ROMs can be obtained using either numerical simulations or experimental data, and the approach extends to flexible tanks. The ROM is purely based on data (Input/Output) and results in an matrix of transfer function matrix of unsteady Generalized Sloshing Force (GSF), analogous to the Generalized Aerodynamic Force (GAF) matrix used in classical linear aeroelasticity. Figure 15 shows the application of the LFD model to the dynamic of a flying wing carrying fuel under the aircraft fuselage. In particular the effect of sloshing on the real and imaginary part of eigenvalues of the aeroelastic system is presented, clearly showing the changes when compared to the "frozen" fluid case. This work has been described in several publications, Ref. [33–36].

An alternative ROM approach was developed by the University of Bristol, constituting in equivalent mechanical models (EMM) of fluid sloshing. As shown in Fig. 16(right), the three key sloshing and damping regions were identified in the experimental data (WP2). The first region (R1) is dominated by the violent, chaotic, and strongly turbulent liquid motions; then, after transiting through the mixed-mode response region the fluid enters the structured and wave-dominated response (R2). The third region (R3) was found to be associated with the liquid activity with negligible influence on the overall behaviour of the system. The initial EMM development centred on the R1 and mixed R1-R2 regions. A simple and highly efficient analytical lumped mass model (16) was used and tuned to model the effect of the impacting fluid in the R1 region. This used a phenomenological EMM where a single free ball was contained and interacting with the upper and lower boundary of the oscillating system. The experimental tests were compared with the numerical simulations and they showed an acceptable and useful representation of the experimental results in the modelled R1 sloshing region. Finally the model was integrated into an aeroelastic framework for the computation of aircraft gust response in Ref. [29].

The ROM approaches developed in the first phase of the project are highly efficient in terms of computation time, and proved capable of modelling the FSI problem. However they present limitations in terms of their applicability to the

Fig. 15 Comparison of Real and Imaginary Parts of Natural Eigenvalues of a Flying Wing with and without the Effect of Sloshing.

Fig. 16 Bouncing Ball Model (Left) and Comparison of Oscillation Decay with Experimental Data and SPH (Right).

different sloshing regimes, in capturing the transition between regimes and in the characterization of violent liquid impacts. These limitations are currently being addressed with more advanced modelling techniques, such as artificial neural networks with promising results.

VIII. Conclusion

The paper provides a review of the progress of the SLOWD H2020 project. A number of the advances are highlighted related to the dynamics of violent sloshing flows when accelerated perpendicular to the free surface. In particular:

- Several novel experimental setups have been devised to investigate the phenomena.
- Different numerical methods have been employed for modelling the fluid and structural dynamics, and validated against experimental data.
- A framework for high-fidelity modelling of the FSI problem has been developed.
- Several techniques for model-order reduction have been investigated and proved capable of describing the major feature of the FSI problem.

Future work will focus on the application of the methods and tools developed to the industrial problem of a flexible wing with partially filled fuel tanks undergoing dynamic excitations, with the ultimate goal of providing a set of recommendations for airliner designers.

Acknowledgments

The SLOWD project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 815044.

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